

Effect of nucleating agents on the characterization of basaltic glass ceramics

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ABSTRACT

Basaltic glass ceramics were prepared successfully based on basalt rocks with successive addition of cement wastes from 10-50 % of the batch constituents, six glass batches are designated G0, G10, G20, G30, G40 and G50, where the number indicates to the weight percent added of the cement waste and the rest is the basaltic rocks. Basaltic rocks were crushed and sieved into 75 μm before mixing with cement waste, the corresponding batches were generally melted in platinum crucibles at 1400 °C for 2h, the melt cast into a steel plate in the form of discs and rods shapes, then transferred to a preheated muffle furnace at 550 °C, which then switched off to cool at room temperature to prevent rupturing the samples, then glass samples subjected to heat treatments at 1000 °C for 2h to induce crystallization and to convert glass into glass ceramics. XRD showed major crystalline phases were Diopside, Anorthite, Gehlenite and Magnetite. SEM showed the microstructure gradually changed from very fine grain into coarse grain microstructure by increasing cement waste ratio, unfortunately the coarse grain microstructure provided a negative effect on the mechanical properties of the obtained glass ceramics, where the microhardness and the bending strength decreased sharply from 6791 to 4077 MPa and from 135 to 77 MPa respectively [1, 2].

For this reason, we studied the effect of some nucleating agents on the microstructure of the obtained glass ceramics which in turn could improve the mechanical properties of the resultant materials. The batch G30 (70% basalt + 30% cement waste) was chosen for study the role of some selected nucleating agents such as Cr_2O_3 , ZrO_2 and CaF_2 , the nucleating agents added to the batch G30 with two different weight ratios as shown 1 and 2 % for Cr_2O_3 and ZrO_2 , and 2 and 4 % for CaF_2 . Six nucleated glass batches are designated G 1Cr, G 2Cr, G 1Zr, G 2Zr, G 2Ca, and G 4Ca, where the numbers indicate the weight ratio added for each selected nucleating agents. Nucleated glass batches melted at 1350-1400 °C according to the batch composition, and then the obtained glass samples subjected to heat treatment at 1000 °C for 2 h to induce the crystallization process.

DTA showed presence of Cr_2O_3 increased the exothermic crystallization peak from 883°C for G30 (nucleating agents free) into 895 °C and 903 °C for G 1Cr and G 2Cr respectively, and regard to addition of ZrO_2 , it's noticed practically increase the viscosity of the produced melts as compared to the basic glass sample (G30) and exothermic temperature reached 910 and 915 °C for G 1Zr and G 2Zr respectively, unlike CaF_2 , It reduced melting temperature as well as the viscosity of the produced melt, also the crystallization exothermic peak decreased to 870, 845°C for G 2Ca and G 4Ca glasses respectively. XRD showed presence of nucleating agents in glass G30 generally facilitates and favors the formation of wollastonite (CaSiO_3), quartz (SiO_2), stabilize formation of diopside ($\text{CaMgSi}_2\text{O}_6$), anorthite ($\text{CaAl}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_8$) and magnetite (Fe_3O_4) [3].

From Fig.1 SEM micrograph, glass ceramics containing Cr_2O_3 showed unsimilar fabrics to the base G30 (nucleating agents free), although both are consisting of ribbon structure of diopside- anorthite, where it showed homogenous fine grained crystals, the average of the crystals sizes of G 2Cr and G 1Cr are 50 nm and 150 nm respectively, while the average crystals size of the base glass ceramic (G30) is 7 μm . The shapes of the crystals of both G 1Cr and G 2Cr are very minute and similar to each other, therefore Cr_2O_3 effectively motivated development uniform bulk crystallization of particularly fine-grained microstructures, while glass ceramics containing ZrO_2 showed rigid cubic crystals with a

great number of crystallization centers, the average of crystals sizes of G 1Zr and G 2Zr are 6 μm and 1 μm respectively, whereas glass ceramics containing CaF_2 showed effectively formation of large non-uniform texture of extremely coarse-grained microstructures which is larger than the base glass ceramic sample, the shapes of the crystals of both of G 2Ca and G 4Ca are fiber and needles shapes, the average crystal size of G 2Ca and G 4Ca is ranging from 50 -150 μm .

According to the mechanical measurements, the nucleated glass ceramic samples have higher microhardness and bending strength values than the base glass ceramics except for CaF_2 nucleated glass ceramics. Sample G 2Cr has the highest microhardness value (5885 MPa), while the corresponding base sample G30 was (4841 MPa) and that reflected the efficacy of Cr_2O_3 nucleating agent for enhancement the microstructure as well as improvement the strength, whereas G 4Ca has the lowest microhardness value (4835 MPa), while samples contained ZrO_2 showed middle effect of microhardness as shown 5400 and 5120 MPa for G 1Zr and G 2Zr respectively. Also it was found that G 2Cr has the highest value of bending strength (141 MPa) and that confirmed how Cr_2O_3 has a great role for initiating homogeneous crystallization which in turn increased the degree of strength, while ZrO_2 has a middle effect on bending strength measurements (95 MPa), G 4Ca has the lowest bending strength value (81 MPa), while bending strength for the base glass ceramic is 88 MPa [3].

Fig.1 SEM micrographs of the base and nucleated glass ceramics

Keywords: Basalt, Cement Waste, Crystallization, Glass Ceramics, Nucleating Agents

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